

Oxidation of α -Amino Acids with Sodium N-Bromo-*p*-Toluene Sulphonamide : A Kinetic Study

D. S. MAHADEVAPPA*, S. ANANDA, (late) M. B. MADE GOWDA and K. S. RANGAPPA

Department of Post-graduate Studies & Research in Chemistry, University of Mysore, Manasagangothri, Mysore-570 006

Manuscript received 16 June 1983, revised 19 November 1983, accepted 13 February 1984

Kinetic investigations of the oxidation of glycine, valine, alanine and leucine by sodium N-bromo-*p*-toluenesulphonamide or bromamine-T (BAT) have been made in acetate buffer of pH 6 (isoelectric pH) at 35°. The rate shows a first order dependence on oxidant concentration but is fractional in [amino acid]. The influence of halide ions, ionic strength, *p*-toluenesulphonamide and varying dielectric constant of medium on the rate has been studied. The formation constant (K_1) and decomposition constant (k_2) of the amino acid-BAT complex have been determined at different temperatures and linear free energy relations have been tested. The rate of oxidation increases in the order leucine > alanine > valine > glycine.

THE chemistry of N-chloro-N-sodiosulphonamides in aqueous solution has received considerable attention¹. The prominent member of this class of compounds namely N-chloro-N-sodio toluene-*p*-sulphonamide (chloramine-T or CAT) is a by-product of saccharin manufacture. The existing literature on the chemistry of CAT and related compounds has been reviewed by Campbell and Johnson². Recently, sodium N-bromotoluene-sulphonamide ($\text{CH}_3-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{NBrNa}\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, bromamine-T or BAT) was introduced³ as an analytical reagent for estimation of diverse reductants in aqueous medium. Formation of free bromine in presence of Br^- ion is observed in some of its reactions. It was of interest to examine the parallel behaviour of this bromamine in comparison to the chlorinating haloamine, CAT, by a mechanistic study of some of its oxidation reactions. Surprisingly, no information is available about the oxidative behaviour of any aromatic bromamine, except for the work of Hardy and Johnston⁴, Ruff and Kuczman⁵ and Singh and Om Prakash⁶.

As a part of our broad programme of mechanistic studies of haloaminometric reactions in general and amino acids in particular, we report the kinetics of oxidation of four amino acids namely, glycine, valine, leucine and alanine near their isoelectric pH by BAT. Studies were carried out in acetate buffer of pH 6 and this isoelectric pH also serves as a point of reference for comparing the kinetic behaviour of the α -amino acids and for understanding the general mechanism of oxidation of these compounds.

Experimental

Preparation of bromamine-T :

Dibromamine-T (DBT) was prepared by the bromination⁷ of chloramine-T. Bromamine-T was

obtained⁸ by dissolving DBT in 4 M NaOH. The purity of BAT was checked iodometrically.

Spectral data of bromamine-T :

The electron impact mass spectrum of BAT was obtained on a Dupont 21-291 mass spectrometer using 70 eV electrons with source and probe temp. at 285 and 50°, respectively. The compound has peaks at m/e 326 (m^+ , weak), 171 ($\text{H}_3\text{C}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{SO}_2\text{NH}_2^+$, strong), 155 ($\text{H}_3\text{C}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{SO}_2^+$) and 91 ($\text{H}_3\text{C}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4^+$).

The uv spectrum of BAT in aqueous solution was obtained with a Beckman DK-2A ratio-recording dual beam spectrophotometer. The compound has a λ_{max} at 224 nm ($\log \epsilon_{\text{max}} = 4.2125$).

The ir spectrum of the compound was recorded on a Perkin Elmer 298 grating infrared spectrophotometer in nujol and showed characteristic bands (cm^{-1}) at 3500 (strong, ν -OH), 2150 (weak, $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$), 1656 (medium δ -OH), 1235 (strong, $\nu_{\text{asym}}-\text{SO}_2$), 1120 (strong, shoulder $\nu_{\text{sym}}-\text{SO}_2$), 1075, 1025 (medium, aromatic in plane δ -CH), 915 (strong, $\nu\text{S}-\text{N}$), 802 (strong, 1,4-disubstituted phenyl ring), 665 (medium, $\nu\text{N}-\text{Br}$) and 615 (medium out of plane ring deformation).

The nmr spectra of BAT were obtained in CDCl_3 using tetramethylsilane (TMS) as the internal standard.

¹H Spectrum : δ (relative to TMS), 2.4 (singlet corresponding to $-\text{CH}_3$), 7.8 (doublet for *ortho* H), 7.4 (doublet for *meta* H). The coupling constant $J_{o,m}$ is 8.0 Hz.

¹³C Spectrum : (ppm relative to TMS), 145.39 (C-1, carbon attached to heteroatom), 140.50 (C-4), 131.75 (C-2,6), 129.40 (C-3,5) and 23.0 (methyl carbon).

An aqueous solution of BAT was standardized by the iodometric method. Glycine (SD/Lab-Chem),

* Present address : Department of Chemistry, University of Saskatchewan, Saskatoon, Sask., Canada.

DL-valine (Loba Chemie), L-leucine (Sisco Research Lab) and L-alanine (B.D.H.) found to be chromatographically pure were further assayed by the acetous-perchloric acid method⁷. Solutions of amino acids were prepared in acetic acid-acetate buffer. All other reagents were of AnalaR grade. Triple distilled water was used throughout.

The reaction was carried out in glass-stoppered pyrex boiling tubes whose outer surface was coated black to eliminate photochemical effects. Appropriate amounts of the amino acid and pH 6 buffer (to keep the total volume constant for all runs) were taken in the tube and thermostated at 35°. A measured amount of BAT solution also thermostated at the same temperature was rapidly added to the mixture in the tube. The progress of the reaction was monitored by iodometric determination of unreacted BAT in an aliquot of the reaction mixture at different intervals of time. The course of the reaction was studied for two half-lives. The pseudo-first order rate constants, *k'*, calculated were reproducible within ±3%.

Stoichiometry :

Varying ratios of BAT to amino acid corresponding to the experimental conditions [amino acid] >> [BAT] were equilibrated in buffer of pH 6 at 35°. The following stoichiometry is suggested from the product analysis

where, R'=H for glycine, (CH₃)₂CH for valine, (CH₃)₂CHCH₂ for leucine and CH₃ for alanine, and R=*p*-CH₃C₆H₄SO₂.

Product analysis :

Ammonia present in the reaction mixture was quantitatively estimated by the microkjeldahl procedure. The aldehydes were detected by preparing their 2,4-DNP derivatives and checking the m.p., *p*-toluenesulfonamide among the reaction products was detected by paper chromatography. Benzyl alcohol saturated with water was used as the solvent with 0.5% vanillin in 1% HCl solution in ethanol as spray reagent (*R_f*=0.905).

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of α-amino acids by BAT were investigated at several initial concentrations of reactants under pH-stat conditions (pH 6). With the substrate in excess, plots of log [BAT]₀/[BAT] vs time are linear indicating a first-order dependence of rate on [BAT] (Fig. 1). A slight induction period was noticed in the case of glycine and valine, but it disappeared at higher concentrations. The pseudo first order rate constants, *k'*, are constant for varying [BAT]₀ and are given in Table 1. Values of *k'* increase when [amino acid]₀ is increased. Plots of log *k'* vs log [amino acid] are linear with slopes of 0.50 (glycine), 0.46 (valine), 0.51 (leucine) and 0.40 (alanine), thus indicating a

Fig. 1. First order plots for the oxidation of (a) valine, (b) glycine, (c) leucine and (d) alanine. [Amino acid]=0.03 M; [BAT]₀=0.005 M; pH=6.0; T=35°. Lower scale on the abscissa refers to glycine.

fractional order dependence of rate on the substrate concentration (Table 1).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF REACTANT CONCENTRATION ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS BY BROMAMINE-T IN BUFFER OF pH 6. Temp : 35°

10 ³ [BAT] ₀ M	10 ³ [Amino acid] M	10 ³ k' sec ⁻¹			
		Glycine	Valine	Leucine	Alanine
2.0	3.0	0.12	—	—	—
3.0	3.0	0.11	0.96	1.75	1.77
4.0	3.0	0.11	0.95	1.73	1.80
5.0	3.0	0.11	0.96	1.82	1.70
6.0	3.0	0.11	0.95	1.69	1.69
7.0	3.0	0.10	0.95	1.63	1.68
8.0	3.0	—	0.92	1.60	1.62
9.0	1.0	—	0.60	1.02	1.05
5.0	2.0	—	0.80	1.47	1.44
5.0	3.0	0.11	0.96	1.82	1.70
5.0	4.0	0.20	1.11	2.03	1.95
5.0	5.0	0.22	1.25	2.13	2.26
5.0	6.0	0.25	1.34	3.06	2.40
5.0	9.0	0.29	—	—	—

Addition of Cl⁻ and Br⁻ had no effect on the rate. Ionic strength of reaction mixture was varied by adding sodium perchlorate (0.1-1.0 M) and the reaction rate was found to be unaffected. Addition of the reaction product *p*-toluenesulfonamide (up to 0.01 M) had no influence on the rate (Table 2). The

dielectric constant of medium was varied by adding different proportions of methanol to the reaction mixture. The rate decreased with increasing proportions of methanol in the case of valine, while the reverse was noticed with glycine. Plots of $\log k'$ vs $\frac{1}{D}$, where D is the dielectric constant of the medium are linear (Fig. 2) with negative slope for valine and positive slope for glycine. However, the rates of oxidation of leucine and alanine are not affected in presence of methanol.

Fig. 2. Effect of varying dielectric constant of medium on the rate of oxidation of amino acids.

[Amino acid] = 0.03 M; [BAT]₀ = 0.005 M; pH = 6.0; T = 35°.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH (μ) AND *p*-TOLUENESULFONAMIDE ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS BY BROMAMINE-T IN BUFFER OF pH 6

μ ([PTS])	$k' \times 10^3 \text{ sec}^{-1}$			
	Glycine	Valine	Leucine	Alanine
0.1 (0.00)	0.11 (0.11)	0.97 (0.96)	1.82 (1.82)	1.70 (1.70)
0.2 (0.001)	0.11 (0.11)	0.97 (0.96)	1.82 (1.83)	1.74 (1.74)
0.4 (0.003)	0.12 (0.12)	0.96 (0.97)	1.82 (1.83)	1.80 (1.82)
0.5 (0.005)	0.12 (0.12)	0.97 (0.98)	1.83 (1.85)	1.78 (1.85)
0.7 (0.01)	0.12 (0.13)	0.98 (0.98)	1.88 (1.92)	1.84 (1.90)
1.0	0.13	—	1.90	—

Values in brackets refer to rate constants in presence of PTS.

Blank experiments performed showed that methanol is not oxidized by BAT under the experimental conditions.

The reactions were studied at different temp. (30–45°) and values of activation parameters are computed (Table 3).

Addition of the reaction mixture to aqueous acrylamide solutions did not initiate polymerization showing the absence of free radical species.

TABLE 3—KINETIC AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS BY BAT IN BUFFER OF pH 6

	Glycine	Valine	Alanine	Leucine
log A	12.7	8.8	8.4	8.6
E _a kJ mol ⁻¹	98.9	65.3	62.3	62.3
ΔH [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹	91.4	62.8	59.7	59.7
ΔS [‡] JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	-23.9	-99.8	-104.0	-102.6
ΔG [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹	98.9	93.6	91.9	91.7

Amino acids are known to exist in the following equilibria in aqueous solutions :

Further, the dissociation of amino acids depends on the pH of the medium. In strongly acidic or alkaline media, the equilibria existing are given by equation (3).

At the isoelectric pH, there is no net migration of the amino acid under an electric potential. Since the amine nitrogen is involved in the reaction sequence it may be assumed that the amino acid reacts in its neutral form.

Bromamine-T (RNBrNa, where R = *p*-CH₃C₆H₄-SO₂) is analogous⁹ to CAT and behaves like a strong electrolyte in aqueous solutions dissociating as :

The anion picks up a proton in acid solutions to give the free acid monobromamine-T, RNHBr.

The free acid has not been isolated but in analogy with the chloro compound, experimental evidence for its formation in acid solutions can be visualised. It undergoes disproportionation.

The dibromamine-T and the free acid hydrolyse to give hypobromous acid (HOBr).

Finally, HOBr ionizes as,

K_a = 2.0 × 10⁻⁹ at 25°.

The possible oxidizing species in acidified BAT solutions are therefore RNHBr, RNBr₂ and HOBr. If RNBr₂ were to be the reactive species, the rate law predicts a second order dependence of rate on [BAT], which is contrary to experimental observations. Further, equation (8) indicates that the hydrolysis is slight and, if HOBr is primarily involved, a first order retardation of rate by the added *p*-toluenesulfonamide is expected. However, no such effect was noticed. Hardy and Johnston⁴ made detailed calculations on the concentration dependence of conjugate acid, HOBr and BrO⁻, on *pH* in aqueous bromamine-B or BAB ($6 \times 10^{-5} M$) in the *pH* range 7-13. It was shown that [RNHBr] is high at *pH* 7 and is of the order of $4.1 \times 10^{-5} M$, while [HOBr] $\approx 6.0 \times 10^{-6} M$ and [BrO⁻] $\approx 10^{-7} M$. The present experiments were conducted at *pH* 6 under which conditions one can still expect a larger concentration of conjugate acid. By extrapolating the results of Hardy and Johnston⁴, we find that [RNHBr] $\approx 3.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ at this *pH* and [HOBr] $\approx 3.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ and [BrO⁻] $\approx 10^{-8} M$. Assuming that the toluene derivative is similar to the benzene analogues, it is quite likely that RNHBr is the oxidizing species which reacts with the substrate. Further, variation of ionic strength of the medium and addition of the reaction product, *p*-toluenesulfonamide have virtually no effect on the rate. Bearing these facts in mind, the following general scheme involving the direct interaction of the substrate with RNHBr in the rate determining step (Scheme 1) is proposed. A fractional order dependence on [substrate] indicates a prior equilibrium followed by the rate limiting step :

In Scheme 1, the amino acid-BAT complex (X) is converted into a N-bromo derivative of the substrate (X') and rate law can be derived as

$$\frac{-d[\text{BAT}]}{dt} = \frac{k_2 K_1 [\text{BAT}]_0 [\text{S}]}{1 + K_1 [\text{S}]} \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) can be transformed into

$$\frac{-d \ln[\text{BAT}]}{dt} = k' = \frac{k_2 K_1 [\text{S}]}{1 + K_1 [\text{S}]} \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{k_2 K_1 [\text{S}]} + \frac{1}{k_2} \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

From the intercept $\left(\frac{1}{k_2}\right)$ and slope of the double reciprocal plot in Fig. 3, k_2 , the decomposition constant, and K_1 , the formation constant, of complex can be calculated for all amino acids. The values

Fig. 3. Double reciprocal plots for the oxidation of amino acids.
[Amino acid] = 0.03 M; [BAT]₀ = 0.005 M; *pH* = 6.0; T = 35°.

at 35° are given below :

Amino acid	K_1 (l.mol ⁻¹)	$10^3 k_2$ sec ⁻¹
Glycine	18.74	0.46
Valine	32.26	2.00
Leucine	42.39	3.22
Alanine	44.24	3.03

Attempts to arrive at a linear free energy relation from the above results and the activation parameters in Table 3 were unsuccessful. Values of k_2 were determined from double reciprocal plots at different temp. (303-318 K) obtained by varying [amino acid]₀ at each temp. (Table 4). The calculated activation parameters for the decomposition of the complex are shown in Table 5. Tests⁹

TABLE 4—RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE DECOMPOSITION OF AMINO ACID-BAT COMPLEX DETERMINED FROM DOUBLE RECIPROCAL PLOTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. K	$k_2 \times 10^3$ sec ⁻¹			
	Glycine	Valine	Alanine	Leucine
303	0.25	1.35	1.94	2.38
308	0.46	2.00	3.08	3.28
313	0.77	3.03	4.54	5.00
318	1.43	4.61	6.89	7.40

TABLE 5—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE DECOMPOSITION OF AMINO ACID-BAT COMPLEX DETERMINED FROM DOUBLE RECIPROCAL PLOTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

	Glycine	Valine	Alanine	Leucine
log A	11.9	9.2	9.1	9.1
E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	89.3	68.0	66.4	64.7
ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	86.7	65.4	63.8	62.1
ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	-38.7	-90.8	-90.8	-94.9
ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	98.8	93.3	94.6	91.4

of the complete Taft equation (equation 13) as well as single parameter correlations for the amino acids were made by the plots of $(\log k_2 - E_S)$ vs σ^* , $\log k_2$ vs σ^* and $\log k_2$ vs E_S . The following regression equations were found :

$$\log (k_2 - E_S) = -4.70 \sigma^* - 2.62 \quad (r=0.9632) \quad \dots \quad (13)$$

$$\log k_2 = -1.153 \sigma^* - 2.71 \quad (r=0.8990) \quad \dots \quad (14)$$

$$\log k_2 = -2.13 E_S - 5.92 \quad (r=0.8989) \quad \dots \quad (15)$$

The poor correlation of k_2 values with the steric substitution constants, E_S , indicates that electronic effects are important, while the implication of steric effects is not clear from equation (14). A negative value of the polar constant, points towards the fact that electron donating centres increase the rate of reaction. However, equation (13) implies that both steric and electronic effects play a role in determining the rate.

It is seen from Table 5 that the rate of oxidation of amino acids increases in the order leucine > alanine > valine > glycine.

The activation energy value is highest for the slowest reaction and vice versa, indicating that it is enthalpy controlled^{9b}. This is further verified by calculating the isokinetic temperature (β) from the slope of the linear plot of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger ($r=0.9979$). The value of β found 424 K is much higher than the temp. range employed in the present work. The fairly high negative ΔS^\ddagger values point towards the formation of a more ordered activated complex and the near constancy of ΔG^\ddagger shows the operation of similar mechanisms for the oxidation of these amino acids by BAT.

The effect of varying solvent composition on the reaction kinetics has been described in detail in the well-known monographs¹⁰⁻¹⁵. For the limiting case of zero angle of approach between two dipoles or an ion-dipole system, Amis¹⁴ has shown that a plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\frac{1}{D}$ gives a straight line with a negative slope for a reaction between a negative ion and a dipole or between two dipoles, while a positive slope results for a positive ion-dipole interaction. While the observation in the case of valine conforms to a dipolar interaction, the increase in rate with a decrease in dielectric constant of the medium noted for glycine and the total absence of the effect of varying dielectric constant on rate in the case of leucine and alanine cannot be explained by the Amis

theory¹⁴. Applying Born equation, Laidler^{11c} has shown the following for a dipole-dipole reaction :

$$\ln k' = \ln k_0 + \frac{3}{8kT} \left(\frac{2}{D} - 1 \right) \left[\frac{\mu_A^2}{r_A^3} + \frac{\mu_B^2}{r_B^3} - \frac{\mu_{AB}^2}{r_{AB}^3} \right] \quad \dots \quad (16)$$

Here k_0 is the rate constant in a medium of infinite dielectric constant. While μ represents the dipole moment, r refers to the radii of reactants and activated complex. It is seen that the rate should be greater in a medium of lower dielectric constant when $r_{AB}^3 > r_A^3 + r_B^3$. The extent of charge dispersion in the transition state is different in the case of glycine. On the other hand $r_{AB}^3 \approx r_A^3 + r_B^3$ implies the absence of dielectric effect of solvent on the rate, as found in the case of leucine and alanine.

A detailed mechanism of oxidation of α -amino acids is given in Scheme 2. An electrophilic attack at the amine nitrogen by Br^+ of $RNHBr$, resulting in the formation of a N-bromo intermediate is envisaged. Subsequent steps are fast and decarboxylation and elimination of H^+ and Br^- ions from the α -imino acid is more or less concerted.

Scheme 2

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Bangalore NMR Facility and Dr. N. M. M. Gowda, University of Texas, Galveston, U.S.A., for spectral data on BAT. One of the authors (M.B.M.) is grateful to Sri Balagan-gadharanatha Swamiji, President, Adichunchanagiri Shikshana Trust and Professor S. T. Nagaraj, Principal, A.I.T., Chikmagalur for encouragement.

References

1. (a) D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, K. S. RANGAPPA, N. M. M. GOWDA and B. T. GOWDA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1981, **85**, 3651; *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1982, **14**, 1183.
- (b) B. T. GOWDA and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin II*, 1983, 823.
2. M. M. CAMPBELL and G. JOHNSON, *Chem. Rev.*, 1978, **78**, 65.
3. (a) C. G. R. NAIR and P. INDRASENAN, *Talanta*, 1976, **23**, 289.
- (b) C. G. R. NAIR, R. L. KUMARI and P. INDRASENAN, *Talanta*, 1978, **25**, 525.
4. F. F. HARDY and J. P. JOHNSTON, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin II*, 1973, 742.
5. F. RUFF and A. KUCSMAN, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin II*, 1982, 1075.
6. R. N. SINGH and OM PRAKASH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1982, **21A**, 616.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Organic Analysis", Longman Green, London, 1958, p. 708.
8. E. Bishop and V. J. JENNINGS, *Talanta*, 1958, **1**, 197.
9. R. D. GILLIOM, "Introduction to Physical Organic Chemistry", Addison-Wesley, London, 1970, (a) p. 156-160; (b) p. 168.
10. E. A. MORLWYN-HUGHES, "The Kinetics of Reaction in Solutions", Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1947.
11. (a) K. J. LAIDLER and H. EYRING, *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1940, **39**, 303.
- (b) K. J. LAIDLER and P. A. LANDSKROENER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **52**, 200.
- (c) K. J. LAIDLER, "Chemical Kinetics", Tata-McGraw Hill, 1965.
12. S. W. BENSON, "The Foundations of Chemical Kinetics", McGraw Hill, New York, 1960.
13. A. A. FROST and R. G. PHARSON, "Kinetics and Mechanism", 2nd Edn., Wiley, New York, 1961.
14. E. S. AMIS, "Solvent Effects on Reaction Rates and Mechanisms", Academic Press, New York, 1966.
15. S. G. ENTELIS and R. P. TIGER, "Reaction Kinetics in the Liquid Phase", Wiley, New York, 1976.